

Observations of Medium Scale Travelling Ionospheric Disturbances in the F-region

Anna Belehaki

Research Director, National Observatory of Athens, Greece

belehaki@noa.gr

Abstract

This technical report analyses signatures of Medium Scale Travelling Ionospheric Disturbances (MSTIDs) in the bottomside ionosphere and in the lower altitudes of the topside ionosphere (F-region). The analysis is based on ionospheric characteristics extracted from ionograms and on in-situ electron density observations from Swarm satellites in the topside ionosphere. This work is part of the EOARD grant “Spatial Trajectory of Travelling Ionospheric Disturbances”.

Introduction

Travelling Ionospheric Disturbances (TIDs) are plasma density fluctuations that propagate as waves through the ionosphere at a wide range of velocities and frequencies. Mayr et al. (1990) have demonstrated with a series of simulation experiments, that perturbations detected in the ionospheric characteristics due to TIDs and the source of their excitation do not have a one-to-one correspondence. This is the reason why, the tracking and even the nowcasting of TIDs is very challenging. However, this is a key issue for operational systems using predictable ionospheric characteristics as they can impose disturbances with amplitudes of up to ~20% of the ambient electron density, and Doppler frequency shifts of the order of 0.5 Hz on HF signals (Reinisch et al., 2018).

Under TIDs, all ionospheric characteristics that define the shape of the Ne profile (i.e. the scale height along the various ionospheric and plasmaspheric layers, and the characteristics at the height of the peak density), are largely affected. Electron density reconstruction models can support the analytical study of the effects of the TIDs in each critical characteristic, as long as the models have a validated performance under TIDs conditions.

In order to develop a methodology for the identification of TIDs, it is important to consider the triggering mechanisms, the propagation characteristics and the climatological pattern:

Ionospheric plasma perturbation with a horizontal wavelength of ~100-500 km is considered as medium-scale traveling ionospheric disturbances (MSTIDs). Phase speed and period of MSTIDs are 250–1000 m/s and 15 min to 1 h, respectively (Hunsucker, 1982). MSTIDs are observed both in the daytime and in the nighttime. In the northern hemisphere (NH), during the daytime, MSTIDs frequently propagate towards the south or southeast direction, and in the nighttime, the preferential propagation direction is southwest with phase front alignment in the northwest to southeast direction. The difference in the propagation direction of MSTIDs suggests that the causative mechanism of daytime and nighttime MSTIDs is different (Kotake et al. 2006). Investigations suggested that daytime MSTIDs are generated in association with primary and/or secondary gravity waves (Frissell et al. 2016) mainly originating in the lower and middle atmosphere, respectively. On the other hand, the nighttime MSTID is caused by the electrodynamic processes i.e. Perkins instability associated with E- and F-region coupling processes (Cosgrove et al. 2004; Makela and Otsuka 2012; Saito et al. 2008).

Recent studies found that the daytime MSTID activity is higher during winter irrespective of longitudes (Sivakandan et al. 2021). Using SuperDARN radar observation, Frissell et al. (2014, 2016) reported the local time dependency and source of the daytime MSTID occurrence and argued that polar atmospheric processes particularly polar vortex variabilities, and stratospheric winds are primarily responsible for controlling the occurrence of high-latitude and mid-latitude winter daytime MSTIDs.

Nighttime MSTIDs show seasonal and longitudinal variations over mid-latitudes. For example, 630 nm airglow and GPS TEC observations showed the occurrence of MSTIDs with two distinct peaks: a primary peak during summer and a secondary peak in winter over the Japanese sector (Otsuka et al. 2021). At the same time, the semiannual variation of nighttime MSTIDs shows maxima during solstices and minima during equinoxes over North America (Martinis et al. 2010) and Europe (Otsuka et al., 2013). It was suggested that Es layers and interhemispheric coupling as a possible generation mechanism of nighttime MSTIDs (Martinis et al., 2010) could instigate the observed semiannual variation. Therefore, the longitudinal variation of Es layer occurrence could be a plausible reason for the longitudinal variation of MSTIDs occurrence (Otsuka et al., 2008).

Hysell et al. (2018) shown observations of mid-latitude F-region plasma density irregularities occurring in tandem with Es-layer irregularities over Arecibo during a geomagnetically quiet period. Previous measurements of mid-latitude spread F at Arecibo and elsewhere have suggested wavelike variations in the height of the F-layer peak. The observations presented by Hysell et al. (2018) are unique in that they show much deeper instability with significant upwelling and overturning in plasma density extending well into the topside. Numerical simulation results of the midlatitude ionosphere have used to explain the most important features in the Arecibo observations including the patchy Es layers, MSTIDs, bottomside spread F irregularities, and irregularities in the topside. The most important ingredient in the simulations are intense gravity waves propagating upward into the thermosphere. The gravity wave wind fields both form the Es layers and cause them to structure, induce MSTIDs through dynamo action, and drive currents in the F region which lead to the formation of bottomside irregularities. Most importantly, the gravity waves induce electric fields in the E region which map along magnetic fields into the topside where they produce irregularities in the topside through convection and advection.

In the following sections we analyze Digisonde observations to determine key properties and behavior of MSTIDs, we use spectral analysis to specify the propagation pattern at regional scale and finally we adopt the topside α -Chapman Swarm-Digisonde (α -C-SD) model (Belehaki et al., 2022) to specify the effect of the MSTID plasma irregularities in the characteristics of the electron density profile.

Methods, Assumptions and Procedures

The following steps are taken:

- Analysis of ionograms and extracted characteristics during periods of MSTID occurrence in three European Digisonde stations, in Dourbes (Belgium), Ebro (Spain), Athens (Greece) that are selected because of the high cadence (5 min) and high-quality data.
- Spectral analysis of iso-ionic data to estimate possible MSTID propagation delays between the three sites, in comparison with the MSTID signatures detected in the ionograms.
- Application of the α -C-SD reconstruction model in one year of data to study the modification of the reconstructed electron density profiles under bottomside irregularity conditions.

Results and discussion

Analysis of Digisonde observations to determine key properties and behavior of MSTIDs

The analysis is based on vertical incidence ionograms collected by three Digisonde stations whose location is presented in Figure 1. Their coordinates are given in Table 1. All stations traditionally provide data of high quality at 5 min cadence. However, under MSTIDs the ionogram traces are distorted by hooks that appear inside or outside the foF2 and fxF2 cusps. The ARTIST 5 ionogram autoscaling is not perfect when there are TIDs disturbing the traces, making the correct scaling of ionograms hard even for humans.

The derivation of the plasma frequency profile usually ignores some of the small-scale structure in the autoscaled trace. In this case, the TID-distorted (red) foF2 cusp has been ignored in favor of one that is consistent with the undisturbed vertical (green) fxF2 cusp (Figure 2).

Figure 1: The location of the three Digisondes whose observations are used in this report

Table 1: The coordinates of the Digisonde stations

Digisonde station	Geographic latitude (N)	Geographic longitude (E)
Athens AT138	38.0	23.5
Dourbes DB049	50.1	4.6
Roquettes (Ebro) EB040	40.8	0.5

Figure 2: Ionograms recorded under MSTIDs

On 25 November 2021, MSTIDs are detected during daytime hours from 0900UT to 1500UT in Europe and are recorded by all three stations. This period is characterized by quiet magnetospheric activity conditions, since the auroral electrojets are very weak on 25 November and the previous day as well, as shown in the AE plots presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3: The AE indices (Kyoto WDC) for 24 and 15 November 2021

To reduce ionogram scaling errors, as much as possible, all the ionospheric characteristics used in this analysis have been extracted with manual scaling of the ionograms, using SAO-X software developed by the UML team.

The iso-ionic electron density contour plot is frequently used as an indicator for TIDs. Here below we present the plot for the time interval under study using automatic scaled ionograms. In Figure 4 we present the iso-ionic contour plots of the true and virtual height for Athens Digisonde using automatic scaled data. The iso-ionic contour plots are shown for the daytime hours (0900 to 1500 UT) from 3.5 MHz to 6.0 MHz with 0.1 MHz step, when enhanced MSTIDs are observed in the ionograms. In Figure 5 the same plots are presented with manually scaled data.

Figure 4: The true height (left) and virtual height (right) iso-ionic contour plots for autoscaled Athens Digisonde data

Figure 5: The true height (left) and virtual height (right) iso-ionic contour plots for manual Athens Digisonde data

An oscillating behavior is clearly observed in both iso-ionic contour plots with a periodicity of ~ 45 min especially from 0900 to 1120 UT and from 1245 to 1500 UT. To inspect with detail the behavior of MSTIDs, we present the ionograms recorded by the three Digisonde stations in these two intervals where the MSTID occurrence is more systematic. In Figure 6 we present the ionograms recorded from 0940 to 1010 UT in 5 min steps and in Figure 7 we present ionograms recorded from 1420 to 1445 UT. In all sequences there is a tendency for the disturbance to progress down at lower frequencies and smaller group delays. This confirms that the higher altitudes are affected first.

Figure 6: Sequence of ionograms showing the propagation of MSTIDs from 0940 to 1010 UT in 5 min steps

To obtain the MSTID characteristics, we present in Figure 8 the true height iso-ionic data plots for the 6 hours sample data obtained on 25 November 2021 from the three Digisonde stations. Here the plots are presented in 4 frequency ranges, 2.0 – 2.8 MHz, 3.0 – 3.8 MHz, 4.0 – 4.8 MHz, 5.0 – 5.8 MHz given that the recordings are taken during daytime hours. The detrended true height iso-ionic data plots are presented in Figure 9.

In Figures 10 and 11 we present the virtual height iso-ionic data plots of the electron density and its detrended values.

Athens, AT138

Dourbes, DB049

Ebro, EB040

Figure 7: Sequence of ionograms showing the propagation of MSTIDs from 1420 to 1445 UT in 5 min steps

TrueHeight

Figure 8: The true height iso-ionic data plots for the 6 hours sample data obtained on 25 November 2021 from the three Digisonde stations

TrueHeight

Figure 9: Same as Figure 8 for detrended iso-ionic data

VirtualHeight

Figure 10: The virtual height iso-ionic data plots for the 6 hours sample data obtained on 25 November 2021 from the three Digisonde stations

VirtualHeight

Figure 11: Same as Figure 10 for detrended iso-ionic data

The most pronounced oscillations are observed in the frequency range from 4.0 to 5.8 MHz. The largest amplitudes are recorded in Athens from 1300 to 1500 UT and in Ebro from 0900 to 1100 UT whereas in Dourbes noticeable oscillations in these plasma frequencies are observed in both time intervals, however they are weaker in amplitude. This indicates a west-east propagation pattern. In an attempt to further confirm this indication, spectral analysis is performed over the detrended iso-ionic data.

Spectral analysis

The Spectral analysis is performed with two methods:

The Lomb Scargle periodogram developed by Lomb (1976) and further extended by Scargle (1982) to find, and test the significance of weak periodic signals with uneven temporal sampling.

The xcorr, that provides the cross correlation between two iso-ionic time series x and y .

The correlation with lag k is defined as $\sum_n x[n+k] * y'[n]$, where y' is the complex conjugate of y .

Lomb-Scargle method: To determine the spectral features due to AGW activity in the data, the Lomb-Scargle method is used. This is a preferred approach due to the presence of data gaps in the time series. Indicative results are shown in Figure 12 for the frequencies 3.2, 3.8, 4.2 and 4.8 MHz. The spectrum obtained from the analysis of Dourbes data shows multiple peaks, with the maximum periodicity from 45 min to 80 min. The spectrum obtained from Ebro data gives periodicities from 35 to 55 min, and for Athens Data the periodicities are 30 min to 40 min. The maximum amplitude is obtained for Athens for the highest frequencies.

Figure 12: Lomb Scargle spectral analysis results for the data obtained within the 6 hours sample data on 25 November 2021, with a 5 min analysis.

XCORR method: The cross-correlation results between Athens, Dourbes and Ebro detrended iso-ionic data are shown in Figure 13. A time lag of the order of 100-120 min is calculated between Ebro and Athens spectra. This agrees with the 2 hours shift seen in the detrended isoionic data series (see Figure 9). The cross correlation between Dourbes and Ebro data gives a time lag of the order of ~35 min for the indicative

frequency range of 3.2 – 3.4 MHz, however the coefficients are too weak to justify a clear propagation pattern.

Figure 13: The cross-correlation XCORR results between Athens, Dourbes and Ebro detrended iso-ionic data

Figure 14: XCORR results between the frequencies [2.8 – 3.0] MHz, [3.6 – 3.8] MHz, [4.4 – 4.6] MHz received in Athens Digisonde from 0900 to 1500 UT.

Figure 15: Same as Figure 14 for Dourbes Digisonde.

Figure 16: Same as Figure 14 for Ebro Digisonde.

The time lag is not constant. Moving from higher frequencies to smaller frequencies, the time lag shifts from ~ 60 min to ~ 30 min, resulted from tilted TID fronts. This trend is also seen in the virtual height iso-ionic contour plots shown indicatively for Athens Digisonde station in Figure 17. The tilted fronts are denoted with the black dashed lines.

Figure 17: The virtual height iso-ionic contour plot for Athens Digisonde station. The tilted wave fronts are denoted with the black dashed lines.

The results from the spectral analysis for this specific case studied here, indicate that the amplitude of the MSTIDs is increased with the wave frequency and towards lower latitudes. Considering that waves of higher frequencies correspond to higher altitudes, a conclusion is that the MSTID amplitude faints as the disturbance move downwards.

The maximum perturbation is detected close to $hmF2$ and even above considering that extra layers are observed above the $hmF2$. Therefore, for a realistic representation of the electron density under MSTID conditions, the bottomside electron density profiles have to be extended few hundreds of km above the $hmF2$ in the topside. It is therefore of significant importance to specify the variability of characteristics that define the shape of the electron profile at the higher layers of the bottomside and the lower layers of the topside ionosphere. This is attempted in the next section.

The variability of the effective scale height

The effective scale height provides a direct and practical approach used for the reconstruction of the electron density (N_e) profile $N_e(h)$ including its topside part. The effective scale height is defined as the scale height in fitting the N_e profiles with the α -Chapman function. Reinisch and Huang (2001) introduced a technique to extrapolate the topside ionosphere based on the information from ground-based ionograms. They approximated $N_e(h)$ around and above the F2 layer peak ($hmF2$) by the α -Chapman function with an effective scale height (H_m) determined at $hmF2$. The ionogram-derived H_m is a kind of measure of the slope of the Digisonde-derived electron density profiles in the topside ionosphere. Reinisch and Huang (2001) assumed that the effective scale height in the topside remains constant and equal to the effective scale height at the $hmF2$ altitude. However, the ionospheric total electron content (ITEC) calculated as the integral of the electron density with altitude resulted with this method, underestimates the plasmaspheric contribution, as shown by Belehaki et al. (2003). Later on, the growing bulk of topside measurements suggested the need to allow for a more general function of the scale height in respect to height (Hernandez – Pajares et al., 2017a; Nsumei et al., 2012; Olivares-Pulido et al., 2016; dos Santos Prol et al., 2019; Wu et al., 2020). The majority of these studies rely on statistical analysis and provide the statistical pattern of the effective scale height variability. Olivares-Pulido et al (2016) presented results based on occultation data from the Constellation Observing System for Meteorology, Ionosphere, and Climate/FORMO SATellite-3 (COSMIC/FORMOSAT-3) Global Positioning System (GPS), inverted by means of the Improved Abel transform inversion technique. They demonstrated that the scale height presents a linear trend above the F2 layer peak height, which is in

good agreement with the expected linear temperature dependence. Results based on data from the northern hemisphere from four individual days suggest that scale height at the maximum of the peak, show significant dependency on LT and latitude. Park et al. (2015) estimated the α -Chapman scale height of the plasma density H_m in the topside ionospheric F-region around the Korean Peninsula using the Swarm constellation and ionosondes in Korea. From the statistical distribution of the scale height with respect to LT and season, it is concluded that H_m above Korean Peninsula exhibits complex seasonal and LT dependence.

In a first attempt to specify the behavior of the effective scale height H_m under the occurrence of MSTIDs, the Digisonde derived H_m is correlated with the $hmF2$ parameter. The analysis is based on more than 60 hours of MSTID activity in November and December 2021 and the results show that large swings in $hmF2$ are followed by the F2 scale height. The corresponding plot that demonstrates this agreement is presented in Figure 18 for the test case of 25 November 2021.

Figure 18: The time plot of the $foF2$, $hmF2$ and H_m characteristics during the hours of MSTID activity on 25 November 2021

The next step is to specify further the connection between the scale height variability in the lower layers of the topside and the irregularities in the bottomside ionosphere. For this purpose, Swarm A and Digisonde stations coincidences have been identified within the interval from September 2015 to August 2016 (Belehaki et al., 2022). The Swarm A and Digisonde observations, to be characterized as coincident must meet the following conditions:

- Spatial condition: collocated observations are considered those acquired within an area centered at the Digisonde station and extends ± 2.5 degrees in latitude and longitude. Each satellite pass above the area of coincidence has a maximum duration of almost 78 sec (i.e. 156 data points) and a spatial range of 300km.
- Temporal condition: the ionosondes perform a vertical incidence sounding within in a time interval of few minutes, while 30 to 90 sec are needed to reach the frequency range of the F-region, depending on the time of the day and on the chosen operational parameters. Swarm A observations to be considered as simultaneous with the Digisonde vertical incident ionogram, must be acquired within the duration of ionosonde sounding up to the time the sounder reaches the cut off frequency $foF2$. This condition, to be satisfied, the satellite must enter the coincidence area from 0 to 30 sec after the start of the sounding.

Based on the criteria above, more than 4000 coincidences have been identified. After performing a quality check on the data, 347 cases were retained for further analysis, among which 125 cases correspond to daytime and nighttime hours and the remaining are coincidences that occurred simultaneously with the solar terminator crossing.

Exploiting coincident observations from Swarm A satellite and from Digisonde stations, it is possible to calculate the scale height at Swarm A altitude, adopting a simple reconstruction model up to Swarm A

altitude. The reconstruction of the topside electron density profile is based on the assumption that the part of the profile above the altitude of $hmF2$ and up to the altitude of Swarm A (~ 450 km) follows the α -Chapman model with a variable scale height referred to here after as α -Chapman - Swarm Digisonde model (α -C-SD model). The reconstruction model has two anchor points: the height and electron density at $hmF2$ provided by the Digisonde, and the height and electron density at the topside provided by Swarm A LP experiment. To reconstruct the profile, coincident Swarm A LP observations with Digisonde stations are exploited.

The effective scale height at the Swarm A altitude, H_T , at Swarm A altitude is calculated, assuming that the electron density above the peak height and up to the satellite altitude, follows the α -Chapman approximation described by equation (1):

$$N_T = NmF2 \exp \left[\frac{1}{2} (1 - z - e^{-z}) \right] \quad (1)$$

$$\text{where } z = \int_{hmF2}^{hs} \frac{dh}{H_T} \quad (2)$$

N_T is the Swarm A LP Ne (electron density, m^{-3})

$NmF2$ is the Digisonde derived peak density Ne at $hmF2$

$hmF2$ is the Digisonde derived true height of the peak density (km)

hs is the Swarm altitude (km)

The $NmF2$ (in m^{-3}) is calculated from the f_oF2 characteristic (in MHz) using the relationship:

$$NmF2 = 1.24 \times 10^{10} \times f_oF2^2.$$

The effective scale height at the Swarm A altitude, H_T , is calculated for each Swarm A observation during its pass over Digisonde, assuming that the electron density at $hmF2$, remains constant during the satellite pass from the coincident area and equal to $NmF2$ measured by the Digisonde. Obviously, the only unknown parameter in equations (1) and (2) as described above is the effective scale height H_T . Equations (1) and (2) are solved utilizing a substitution numerical method. In particular, a numerical solution is sought to minimize the difference between the left and the right-hand sides of the equation (1). A solution is assumed of being valid only in the case when the difference is smaller than 0.0001 or the difference is smaller than 0.0001 times $NmF2$. Having calculated the effective scale height H_T at ~ 450 km, the function of the electron density with altitude can be estimated from the altitude of the $hmF2$ to the altitude of the Swarm A satellite, increasing the altitude by 10 km, to follow the height resolution of the Digisonde measurements and get a continuous electron density profile from the 90km up to the Swarm A altitude. Indicative cases for the reconstructed electron density profiles with the α -C-SD model are presented in Figure 19 for a daytime and a nighttime ionogram. In the right-side plot of both figures, two electron density profiles are overplotted:

1. The Digisonde profile (black line) - The electron density profile obtained directly from the SAO file (<https://ulcar.uml.edu/~iag/SAO-4.htm>); it is important to underline that the topside part is an α -Chapman approximation with constant effective scale height and equal to the effective scale height at the $hmF2$, denoted in the plots as H_B (Huang and Reinisch, 2001). This is certainly a simplification, and it is presented here only as a reference topside profile.
2. The α -C-SD profile (red line) - The electron density profile obtained at the topside using an α -Chapman function assuming a variable effective scale height which depends on the electron density measured at Swarm A altitude;

The Ne characteristic observed from Swarm A LP during its pass along the coincident area (a maximum duration of 78 sec), is indicated with the green line. The mean H_T calculated during the pass of the satellite from the coincidence area, its range δH_T , and the corresponding effective scale height at $hmF2$ (H_B) are given for each case. In both cases presented here, the scale height in the topside gets higher values than at $hmF2$.

The Eglin AFB ionogram indicates normal stratified ionosphere. For this case, the topside scale height values have a range (δH_T) of 1.49 km, or 3% variability in respect to the mean value. The conditions extracted from the Ramey ionogram, denote the occurrence of a MSTID or a strong spread F. For this case, the topside

effective scale height calculated during the satellite pass from the coincidence area has a mean value of 77.09 km with a variability of 37% in respect to the mean value.

The analysis of these examples, provides evidence for possible connection between bottomside irregularities and high variability in the scale height H_T at Swarm A altitude. Consequently, the possibility to consider the variability of H_T as an indicator for the local plasma instability in the topside, is further investigated.

Figure 19: Examples that demonstrate the performance of the topside reconstruction α -C-SD model

The results extracted from all coincidences included in this study, are used to investigate the diurnal variation of the effective scale heights at $hmF2$ and at the Swarm A altitude (lower part of the topside ionosphere). The diurnal variation with Local Time for the two characteristics is presented in Figure 20. The average value with its standard deviation is calculated based on all the coincidences identified within each hour of the day. The bottomside scale height H_B exhibits a daily variation with the higher values around noon time. On the contrary, the daily variation pattern of the topside scale height H_T , exhibits two maxima – one in the early morning and another in the evening hours. At night-time hours, the effective scale height in the topside is in general larger than at $hmF2$, which indicates a trend for an increase with altitude above the $hmF2$. During day-time hours, the two scale heights have comparable magnitudes.

In the analysis that follows, the mean value of the topside effective scale height H_T is calculated for each Swarm A pass over Digisonde, with its gradient ∇H_T , and it is compared with the effective scale height at the $hmF2$, H_B , provided by coincident Digisonde manually scaled ionograms. The results are shown in Figure 21 grouped by nighttime and daytime cases. Here the cases that correspond to the crossing of the solar terminator are excluded. The top panels show the variation of the bottomside effective scale height (orange-colored symbols) and of the topside effective scale height (blue-colored symbols) as a function of the Swarm

A distance from $hmF2$. The range of the effective scale height variability is marked with vertical bars. The bottom panels in Figure 21, present the frequency spread (FF) with blue symbols and the range spread F (QF) with orange symbols versus the distance of the satellite from the height of the peak electron density, i.e. from $hmF2$. This graphical representation intends to provide information about the irregularities in the bottomside, recorded while Swarm A was passing over the Digisonde stations.

Figure 20: The average value and the standard deviation of the bottomside and the topside effective scale heights calculated based on all the coincidences identified within the hour in Local Times

The first remark is that the Swarm A distance from the $hmF2$ is always positive, confirming that the satellite is always at the topside, for the cases considered in this analysis.

Figure 21: Scale Height as a function of the satellite distance from $hmF2$, under nighttime and daytime Swarm-Digisonde coincidences

Regarding the mean value of the effective scale height H_T calculated during the satellite pass over the Digisonde coincident area, Figure 21 indicates that for the night-time cases, the mean H_T is comparable to the bottomside scale height H_B when $hmF2$ distance from Swarm A is smaller than ~ 120 km. For larger distances, i.e. when the $hmF2$ drops below 330 km, the bottomside scale height decreases and deviates significantly from the topside scale height values. During day-time passes, and for short distance of $hmF2$ from Swarm A (less than 200 km), the bottomside scale height H_B tends to be larger than the topside scale height H_T . As the $hmF2$ drops to lower altitudes, the effective scale height at Swarm A altitude becomes larger than the effective scale height at $hmF2$. The cases for which Swarm A distance from $hmF2$ is very large, are only a few and are considered to be extreme cases. For all these extreme cases, the range of the topside scale height variability is considerably large, while strong spread F is observed in the corresponding ionograms. Overall, there is a linear positive trend for the effective scale height to increase above the level of the $hmF2$ in nighttime cases. However, in the daytime cases, the linear trend is not obvious especially if the extreme cases are excluded. A complex behavior is rather observed with the two characteristics competing each other in magnitude. As pointed out by Park et al (2015), statistical distributions of the topside scale height, revealed from the analysis of Swarm scale height over Korea, exhibited a complex dependence upon local time and season. This does not fully agree with the general concept for a linear increase of the scale height with altitude above the height of the peak density.

To summarize the observations from Figure 20 and Figure 21:

- For the nighttime cases, the topside effective scale height at 450 km altitude, has a mean value of ~ 56 km and is higher than the effective scale height at $hmF2$. At local spatial scales, its variability is higher when the satellite is closer to the height of the peak density $hmF2$. When the $F2$ layer drops to lower altitudes, the bottomside scale height is decreasing and its magnitude deviates from the effective scale height at Swarm A location.
- For daytime cases, the effective scale height variability at 450 km has a mean value of ~ 52 km and gets general lower values compared to the nighttime cases; its mean value is comparable to the scale height at $hmF2$ only when the distance of Swarm A from $hmF2$ is short and up to 250 km. When $hmF2$ drops further down, the magnitude of the topside and bottomside effective scale height deviate significantly.
- The bottomside effective scale height exhibits a diurnal variation with its maximum around noon. The diurnal pattern of the topside effective scale height at ~ 450 km presents two maxima in the early morning and evening hours.

Conclusions

The identification of MSTIDs is primarily based on ionograms that shows mainly forked and multi-cusp traces. The detrended iso-density contour plots provide additional information about the periodicity of the MSTIDs, while simultaneous analysis of observations from several Digisonde stations located at a distance of ~ 1000 km, provides the following indications regarding the propagation pattern during daytime hours in the European sector fall and winter months:

- The amplitude of the MSTIDs increases with the wave frequency and towards lower latitudes. Considering that waves of higher frequencies correspond to higher altitudes, a conclusion is that the MSTID amplitude faints as the disturbance moves at lower F region altitudes.
- There is evidence for eastward propagation of MSTIDs.

The analysis of Digisonde characteristics and of coincident Swarm A observations leads to the following preliminary conclusions:

- The effective scale height at middle latitudes above the height of the peak electron density remains relatively stable during the daytime hours around the local noon, while in the nighttime, early morning and evening sectors an increase with the altitude is inferred from the data analyzed here that cover the period from September 2015 to August 2016.

- The gradient of the topside effective scale height during the satellite pass over the Digisonde station, can be considered as an indicator for irregularities in the topside which are observed simultaneously with spread F and MSTIDs in the bottomside ionosphere.
- Variations in the F2 effective scale height during the occurrence of MSTIDs, are positively correlated with variations in the height of the F2 peak density.

In the following period of this project, we will continue the analysis of extended time series of ionograms, ionospheric characteristics and Swarm data in order to specify and model the behaviour of MSTIDs in the higher layers of F2 and above.

References

Belehaki, A., Jakowski, N., Reinisch, B.W. (2003), Comparison of ionospheric ionization measurements over Athens using ground ionosonde and GPS-derived TEC values. *Radio Science*, Vol. 38, NO. 6, 1105, doi:10.1029/2003RS002868

Belehaki, A., Tsagouri, I., & Paouris, E. (2022). Characteristics of the effective scale height in the topside ionosphere extracted from Swarm A and Digisonde observations: Preliminary results. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics*, 127, e2021JA030075. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2021JA030075>

Cosgrove, R. B., Tsunoda, R. T., Fukao, S., and Yamamoto, M. (2004), Coupling of the Perkins instability and the sporadic E layer instability derived from physical arguments, *J. Geophys. Res.*, 109, A06301, doi:10.1029/2003JA010295.

Dos Santos Prol, F., Themens, D.R., Hernández-Pajares, M. et al., (2019), Linear Vary-Chap topside electron density model with topside sounder and radio-occultation data. *Surv. Geophys.* <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10712-019-09521-3>.

Frissell, N. A., Baker, J. B. H., Ruohoniemi, J. M., Greenwald, R. A., Gerrard, A. J., Miller, E. S., and West, M. L. (2016), Sources and characteristics of medium-scale traveling ionospheric disturbances observed by high-frequency radars in the North American sector, *J. Geophys. Res. Space Physics*, 121, 3722– 3739, doi:10.1002/2015JA022168.

Frissell, N. A., Baker, J. B. H., Ruohoniemi, J. M., Gerrard, A. J., Miller, E. S., Marini, J. P., West, M. L., and Bristow, W. A. (2014), Climatology of medium-scale traveling ionospheric disturbances observed by the midlatitude Blackstone SuperDARN radar, *J. Geophys. Res. Space Physics*, 119, 7679– 7697, doi:10.1002/2014JA019870.

Hernández-Pajares, M., Garcia-Fernández, M., Rius, A., Notarpietro, R., A. von Engel, G. Olivares-Pulido, À. Aragón-Àngel, and A. García-Rigo (2017a), Electron density extrapolation above F2 peak by the linear Vary-Chap model supporting new Global Navigation Satellite Systems-LEO occultation missions, *J. Geophys. Res. Space Physics*, 122, 9003–9014, doi:10.1002/2017JA023876

Huang, X., and Reinisch, B. W. (2001), Vertical electron content from ionograms in real time, *Radio Sci.*, 36, 335–342. <https://doi.org/10.1029/1999RS002409>

Hunsucker R. D. 1982. Atmospheric gravity waves generated in the high-latitude ionosphere: a review. *Rev. Geophys. and Space Phys.* 20 (2) 293-315. doi:10.1029/RG020i002p00293

Hysell, D., Larsen, M., Fritts, D., Laughman, B. & Sulzer, M., (2018), Major upwelling and overturning in the mid-latitude F region ionosphere, *Nature Communications*, 9:3326 | DOI: 10.1038/s41467-018-05809-x

Kotake N, Otsuka Y, Tsugawa T et al (2006) Climatological study of GPS total electron content variations caused by medium-scale traveling ionospheric disturbances. *J Geophys Res* 111:1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2005J A0114 18>

- Kutiev, I., P. Marinov, and A. Belehaki. 2016. Real time 3-D electron density reconstruction over Europe by using TaD profiler, *Radio Sci.*, 51, 1176–1187, doi:10.1002/2015RS005932.
- Lomb, N.R., (1976), Least-squares frequency analysis of unequally spaced data, *Astrophysics and Space Science*, vol 39, pp. 447-462.
- Makela JJ, Otsuka Y (2012) Overview of nighttime ionospheric instabilities at low- and mid-latitudes: coupling aspects resulting in structuring at the mesoscale. *Space Sci Rev* 168:419–440. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11214-011-9816-6>
- Martinis, C., Baumgardner, J., Wroten, J., & Mendillo, M. (2010). Seasonal dependence of MSTIDs obtained from 630.0 nm airglow imaging at Arecibo. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 37(11), 2000–2004. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2010GL043569>
- Mayr, H. G., Harris, I., Herrero, F. A., Spencer, N. W., Varosi, F., & Pesnell, W. D.. 1990. Thermospheric gravity waves - Observations and interpretation using the transfer function model (TFM), *Space Science Reviews* (ISSN 0038-6308), vol. 54, p. 297-375. doi:10.1007/BF00177800
- Morgan, M. G., and K. A. Ballard. 1978, The height dependence of wave-normal depression and disturbance amplitude in TID's, *J. Geophys. Res.*, 83(A12), 5741-5744. doi:10.1029/JA083iA12p05741
- Nsumeji, P., Reinisch, B. W., Huang, X. & Bilitza, D. (2012), New Vary-Chap profile of the topside ionosphere electron density distribution for use with the IRI model and the GIRO real time data. *Radio Sci.* 47, RS0L16. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2012R S0049 89>.
- Olivares-Pulido, G., Hernández-Pajares, M., Aragón-Angel, A. and Garcia-Rigo, A. (2016), A linear scale height Chapman model supported by GNSS occultation measurements, *J. Geophys. Res. Space Physics*, 121, doi:10.1002/2016JA022337.
- Otsuka Y, Suzuki K, Nakagawa S et al (2013). GPS observations of medium-scale traveling ionospheric disturbances over Europe. *Ann Geophys*, <https://doi.org/10.5194/angeo -31-163-2013>
- Otsuka, Y., Shinbori, A., Tsugawa, T., & Nishioka, M. (2021). Solar activity dependence of medium-scale traveling ionospheric disturbances using GPS receivers in Japan. *Earth, Planets and Space*, 73(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40623-020-01353-5 847>
- Otsuka, Y., Tani, T., Tsugawa, T., Ogawa, T., & Saito, A. (2008). Statistical study of relationship between medium-scale traveling ionospheric disturbance and sporadic E layer activities in summer night over Japan. *Journal of Atmospheric and Solar-Terrestrial Physics*, 70(17), 2196–2202. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jastp.2008.07.008>
- Park, J., Kwak, Y.-S., Mun, J.-C., Min, K.- W. (2015), Vertical Scale Height of the Topside Ionosphere Around the Korean Peninsula: Estimates from Ionosondes and the Swarm Constellation, *J. Astron. Space Sci.* 32(4), 311-315, doi:10.5140/JASS.2015.32.4.311
- Reinisch, B. W., & Huang, X. (2001). Deducing topside profiles and total electron content from bottomside ionograms, *Adv. Space Res.*, 27(1), 23–30.
- Reinisch, B., Galkin, I., Belehaki, A., et al. 2018. Pilot ionosonde network for identification of traveling ionospheric disturbances, *Radio Science*, 53, 365–378. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2017RS006263>
- Saito, S., Yamamoto, M., and Hashiguchi, H (2008). Imaging observations of nighttime mid-latitude F-region field-aligned irregularities by an MU radar ultra-multi-channel system, *Ann. Geophys.*, 26, 2345–2352, <https://doi.org/10.5194/angeo-26-2345-2008>.
- Scargle J.D., (1982), Studies in astronomical time series analysis. II - Statistical aspects of spectral analysis of unevenly spaced data”, *The Astrophysical Journal*, vol 263, pp. 835-853.
- Sivakandan, M., Otsuka, Y., Ghosh, P. et al. 2021. Comparison of seasonal and longitudinal variation of daytime MSTID activity using GPS observation and GAIA simulations. *Earth Planets Space* 73, 35 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40623-021-01369-5>

Wu, M. J., Guo, P., Chen, Y.L., Fu, N.F., Hu, X.G., Hong, Z.J. (2020), New Vary-Chap scale height profile retrieved from COSMIC radio occultation data. *J. Geophys. Res. Space Phys.* 125, e2019JA027637. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2019JA027637>